

SHAPING 'GREEN TRANSFORMATION' WITHIN CHANGING CONTEXTS IN IR

Asqarova Shaxnoza Botirovna

Master's student of International Relations and World Politics
University of World Economy and Diplomacy
100157, Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Chilanzar District, 25
Tel: +99899 606-70-14, e-mail: shaxnozaasqarova9@gmail.com
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Abstract

Green transformation has become one of the critical directions in the further development of the world [1.1] and needless to say, the reasons behind the emergence of this phenomena are global warming and climate change. Being critical direction in the development of the world, "green transformation" has started to be reflected as an agenda in IR also and in the formation of "green transformation" in modern international relations, discourse of global warming and climate change plays pivotal role. In this article, formation of "green transformation" in changing contexts of modern international relations will be researched by exploring how global warming entered in politics and became political issue. Various perspectives of politicians and the public opinion about global warming will be learned with the help of Discourses of Global Warming and Climate Change.

Key words: Green Transformation, Climate Change, Climate Chang Discourse, Industrial Fatalism, Green Keynesianism, Eco-Socialism, Climate Skepticism.

Green transformation is a combination of economic growth with the care about the environment in order to guarantee a high quality of life for present and future generations at the level which is attainable due to civilizational development, as well as to an effective and rational use of the available resources [2.2]. Needless to say, a key to the emergence of green transformation in the society and in IR is the environmental problems called Climate change and global warming.

Being the root cause of the generation of green transformation as a social process, Climate change and global warming's scope and complexity are difficult to describe. Because these are the problems that sources virtually everywhere, including nearly all kinds of human activity such as agriculture, transportation, manufacturing, energy use, land use, and those have impacts that are being and will be felt across the globe.

Concerns about increasing carbon dioxide emissions, particularly from industry, transportation, and the production of electricity and heat, can lead to profound

climate change have been an increasing part of the international political debate since at least the late 1960s [3.2]. However, until 2006 climate change had been treated by the majority of politicians and other elite actors as just one of several managerial issues relating to the environment and as something to keep an eye on in the future. In 2006 this trend changed dramatically. The issue of global climate change was started to be portrayed in apocalyptic terms, along with recommendations for conservative actions from the autumn of 2006 through to 2009.

In 2007, the issue of global climate change received an unprecedented amount of public and political attention, which culminated in the awarding of the Nobel Peace Prize to Al Gore and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) [4.3]. The more scientific findings of the IPCC were revealed to the Globe by mass media, the more climate change become an agenda of politics.

During the last ten years, growing scientific ideas about anthropogenic effects on the global climate and the significant risks caused to humans and non-human life by the rising levels of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere that are causing climate change has emerged. Indeed, there is obvious scientific agreement that more greenhouse gases are being created today than the period prior to the era of industrialization. According to the scientists that directly involved in researching the issue, human activities are heating up our planet and causing climate change. For instance, in a quantitative research project in 2009 [5.3], Doran and Zimmerman found that 97 per cent of climate scientists agreed that emissions of greenhouse gases generated by humans, namely methane and carbon dioxide, are contributing to anthropogenic climate change. Yet, this scientific agreement disagrees with the opinions of society. Analysis of mass media and internet communication regarding climate change discloses a controversial debate about the existence and reasons behind climate change and how to deal with it, in other words, a debate that reflects denial, doubt and apathy [6.3]. Framing the issue as a debate between believers and deniers of climate change underestimates the fact that it is a complex mix of values and ideas drawn from science, technology, political ecology, value systems, identities, infrastructures and “need” politics [7.4]. Climate change has become political, thus, different actors with different discourses can be found in the international political field as well as in the society and among those various discourses the core ones are Industrial Fatalism, Green Keynesianism, Eco-Socialism, Climate Skepticism which are very different discourses developed along politically divergent paths. Although, representatives of these four discourses equally

acknowledged that urgent actions against the emissions and climate change should be implemented in order for the survival of civilization, the solutions were far from the same.

These four core discourses discuss the issues of a globally equitable distribution of the Earth's resources and responsibility for promoting such a scheme or the roles of technology and science in developing measures to address the problem of climate change and the value-based and epistemological problems that were associated with it, or the potentials of relationship between nature and industrial society that should be the basis for the design of climate action to ensure the long-term survival of contemporary civilization and try to find solutions for these issues. The increasing tensions and disagreements that these discourses articulated were based on fundamental social questions: what constituted a "good" society? Was economic growth part of the solution or part of the problem? What did an ecologically healthy relationship between politics and the market look like? Had significant changes in lifestyles and consumption patterns in the wealthier part of the world become ecologically necessary, or was it enough to simply have environmental labelling of consumer goods? [8.5]

"Industrial Fatalism", which is the dominant climate change and climate mitigation discourse in IR, is shaped by the actors who are mainly representatives of the four political parties in the Liberal-Conservative government coalition, the organizations of trade and industry, and parts of the labor movement and the daily newspapers of Sweden [9.5] concerns that climate change was in principle a dissolvable issue, the solution to which would also positively influence many other issues without risking the future of modern industrial society. This discourse was pervaded by the faith that climate change could be mitigated through international negotiations and agreements on CO₂ emission caps and this belief was founded on the idea that this global threat would force all countries of the world to cooperate.[10.5] Industrial Fatalists assumed that, all countries should have a mutual interest in preventing a global climate collapse, in spite of their different cultural and economic preconditions and that scientific consensus would facilitate rational political management of the problem. Trust in the sanity of the international processes of negotiations and planning indicated that merely slight changes in fundamental economic and technological structures of industrial capitalism were necessary. The fatalists claimed that law, economy, natural sciences and technology would resolve the crisis. Interestingly enough, long-standing arguments for nuclear power were now reutilized to coincide with the

“nuclear renaissance”, as it was universally nicknamed by its proponents [11.5]. Fatalism depicts nuclear power as the only possible alternative to fossil fuels.

At the same time, as the most prevalent discourse that opposed Industrial Fatalism, “Green Keynesianism” appeared in the global climate debate. This discourse also shaped in political arena of Sweden and main representative of this the second most dominant discourse across the globe were environmental organizations such as the Green Party, the Left Party, Social Democrats, and some scientists and political intellectuals whose ideas could be read in the daily press, opinion pages and in journals. Green Keynesianism is characterized by deeper reflections on how side effects of industrial society should be dealt. When Industrial Fatalism advocates that the problem could be handled through new large-scale technical solutions, market solutions and international agreements, Green Keynesianism raises questions about society’s technical, political and economic foundations. Climate change is portrayed in this discourse not as an isolated management problem, but rather as one of many symptoms of a more serious institutional ecological crisis, which demands not only a shift in the relationship between industrial civilization and nature, but also a change in the global distribution of resources and the distribution of the ecological footprint generated by the world’s inhabitants. For instance, Green Keynesians required politicians to take a number of specific steps, such as to compensate for the rich world’s ecological debt to poor countries through comprehensive reductions in carbon emissions in wealthy countries while at the same time landing a helping hand to poor countries, so that they could develop their economies without creating excessive carbon emissions. Actors within the Green Keynesian discourse also highlighted the significance of signing international agreements. However, it is notable, that Green Keynesianism depends on the same systems of science, economy and values typical of ecological modernization that permeate Industrial Fatalism.

Eco-socialism is another core discourse that criticized economic growth as a measure of prosperity and argued for small-scale industry, decentralization and renewable energy technologies [12.7]. The Eco-socialist discourse in Sweden shaped the year that alternative meetings were organized in order to oppose the UN conference in Stockholm, in around 1972. During the period of 1972 until early 1990, an Eco-socialist critique was influential. However, in early 1990, Eco-modern discourses in the forms of Industrial Fatalism and Green Keynesianism, and their actors, moved to the center of the energy and environmental debate: and they pushed the Eco-socialist critique to the margins [13.7]. Until the

apocalyptic climate debate initiated it seemed as if their suggestions were disused; they were absolutely non-existent in the public arena. However, the articulation of climate-change politics as antagonistic during the years between 2006 and 2009 became a victory for the Eco-socialists.

Eco-socialism argued that environmentally unsustainable development was inherent to capitalism, thus, it must be abolished and replaced by democratic socialism [14.7]. It was argued that with the help of eco-socialism people could end their isolation from nature and from each other, which was the biggest cause of environmental degradation. It would require collective political action and opinion formation to bring about climate-friendly decisions according to Eco socialists and this process could be extra-parliamentary and may include occupations and boycotts, but it could also consist of appeals, mass demonstrations and the creation of local groups of people who were endeavoring in living climate-friendly lifestyles. Closely related was the idea that the discourse contained both strong rationalist and romantic images of a climate-friendly society.

Climate change was promoted globally as a matter of apocalyptic dimensions from the autumn of 2006 until 2009. The Industrial Fatalist discourse and Green Keynesianism along with their Eco-socialist counterpart discourse agreed on the seriousness of the situation and its introduction as a comic apocalyptic framing was part of all the discourses. However, there was another small group of Climate Sceptics in the public sphere that consisted of elderly men with influential positions in academia or large private companies. Although, representatives of this group claimed the climate change as an issue of civilizational dimensions, they did not agree with the majority of scientists regarding the anthropogenic reason of climate change, or the need to expedite drastic changes in Western society.

Climate skepticism discourse was characterized by strong beliefs in a market society, a big mistrust of government ruling, and a strong faith in engineering and rational natural science. Representatives of this discourse described themselves as marginalized, banned and oppressed dissidents who felt forced to speak against a faith-based belief in climate science. Another significant element in the discourse was the conservation of industrial society, of which the sceptics were a part, from the values of eco-modern practice. These sceptics argue that humankind is not responsible for global warming, conversely, climate change is all part of the Earth's natural cycle.

Those discourses introduced Climate change into the international political sector in a variety of ways and represent the causes of it also differently, at the same time, the solutions they provide for the issue are also different. But, representatives of exactly those four discourses have had huge influence in shaping “Green transformation” in the changing context of IR. Particularly, the actions they offered to take in order for the resolution of global warming and climate change became the significant contributor in the creation of notions about “green transformation” in IR system.

Использованная литература:

1. Directions of green transformation of the European Union countries
2. Katarzyna Heba, Iwona Bak, Katarzyna Szopik-Depczyńska, Giuseppe Ioppolo .2022
- 2.2 Directions of green transformation of the European Union countries by Katarzyna Cheba, Iwona Bąka, Katarzyna Szopik-Depczyńskab, Giuseppe Ioppolo (2021)
3. 3.2 The Discovery of Global Warming by Spencer R. Weart (2008)
4. 4.3 Securitizing Global Warming A climate of complexity. Delf Rothe (2016)
5. 5.3 Examining the Scientific Consensus on Climate Change by Peter T. Doran, Maggie Kendall Zimmerman (2009)
6. 6.3 Global Environmental Change. L. Whitmarsh (2011)
7. 7.4 Discourses of Climate Change by Jonas Anshelm, Martin Hultman (2014)
8. 8.5 Discourses of Climate Change by Jonas Anshelm, Martin Hultman (2014)
9. 9.5 Ecological Politics in an Age of Risk, Ulrich Beck 1995
10. 10.5 Discourses of Global Climate change, J. Anshelm. 2
11. 11.5 Energy security and climate change. Rogers-Hayden 2011
12. 12.7 Air Pollutants in Germany: Long Term Trends in Deposition and Air Concentration. Gauger, F. Anshelm.2000
13. 13.7 Innovation and Technology for Green Growth, Hultman.2010
14. 14.7 Ecological Utopias: Envisioning the Sustainable Society. de Geus, M. 1999

